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Hawaii Longline Observer Program

Project (PRJ) | Pacific Islands Regional Office (PIRO)

GUID: gov.noaa.nmfs.inport:16865 | Updated: August 9, 2022 | Published / External

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Item Identification

Title: Hawaii Longline Observer Program

Short Name: HILOP

Status: In Work

Abstract: Deploys fishery observers on Hawaii longline fishing vessels targeting tuna (deep set) or swordfish (shallow set) to record information on gear, catch information, morphometrics, specimen collection, environmental data and interactions with protective species such as sea turtles, marine mammals and seabirds.

Purpose: Through an amendment to the pelagic fishery management plan established under the Magnuson-Stevens Fishery Conservation and Management Act, mandatory observers are required aboard Hawaii based pelagic longline vessels targeting swordfish (shallow set, 100% coverage) and tunas (deep set, 20% coverage).

Protected species that interact with the fishery include sea turtles, especially loggerhead (*Caretta caretta*), leatherback (*Dermochelys coriacea*) and green turtles (*Chelonia mydas*). Also seabirds such as the Laysan albatross (*Phoebastria immutabilis*) and black-footed albatross (*P. nigripes*), and to a lesser extent, a few whale and dolphin species.

The observer program is responsible for fielding longline observers to obtain data on incidental sea turtle take and collect fishing effort data. The observers document interactions of all protected species, tally fish that are kept and discarded, and process selected specimens for life history information.

The Pacific Islands Region uses observer data to calculate official estimates (e.g. protected species interactions) and produce technical reports. The Pacific

Islands Fisheries Science Center receives biological samples for analysis.

 Keywords

Theme Keywords

Thesaurus	Keyword
UNCONTROLLED	
None	Acanthocybium solandri
None	albacore tuna
None	Alepisaurus ferox
None	Alopias pelagicus
None	Alopias spp.
None	Alopias superciliosus
None	Alopias vulpinus
None	Anous spp.
None	Assurger anzac
None	Aves
None	Baird's beaked whale
None	Balaenoptera acutorostrata
None	Balaenoptera borealis
None	Balaenoptera edeni
None	Balaenoptera musculus
None	Balaenoptera physalus
None	Balistidae spp.
None	Berardius bairdii
None	bigeye sand tiger shark

None	bigeye thresher shark
None	bigeye tuna
None	Billfishes
None	black gemfish
None	black legged kittiwake
None	black marlin
None	black-footed albatross
None	black/brown noddy
None	blacktip shark
None	Blainville's beaked whale
None	blue marlin
None	blue shark
None	blue whale
None	blue-gray noddy
None	bluefin tuna
None	bottlenose dolphin
None	brama pomfret
None	Brama spp.
None	brown booby
None	bryde's whale
None	bycatch
None	Canthidermis maculata
None	Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos
None	Carcharhinus falciformis

None	Carcharhinus galapagensis
None	Carcharhinus limbatus
None	Carcharhinus longimanus
None	Carcharhinus plumbeus
None	Carcharodon carcharius
None	Caretta caretta
None	Cetacea
None	Chelonia mydas
None	Chelonidae spp.
None	Chondrichthyes
None	cigarfishes
None	common mola
None	common thresher shark
None	cookie cutter shark
None	Coryphaena equiselis
None	Coryphaena hippurus
None	cottonmouth jack
None	crestfishes
None	crocodile shark
None	Cubiceps spp.
None	Cuvier's beaked whale
None	dagger pomfret
None	deep set
None	deepwater dogfishes

None	Delphinidae
None	Delphinus spp.
None	Dermochelys coriacea
None	dolphinfish
None	Echeneidae spp.
None	Elagatis bipinnulatus
None	Eretmochelys imbricata
None	Eschrichtius robustus
None	escolar
None	Eumegistus illustris
None	false killer whale
None	Feresa attenuata
None	fin whale
None	fishery data
None	Fraser's dolphin
None	Fregata spp.
None	Galapagos shark
None	Galeocerdo cuvier
None	Gempylidae spp.
None	Gempylus serpens
None	giant manta ray
None	Globicephala macrorhynchus
None	Gnathastomata
None	Grampus griseus

None	gray reef shark
None	gray whale
None	great barracuda
None	great white shark
None	green sea turtle
None	green turtle
None	hammerjaw
None	Hawaiian monk seal
None	hawksbill sea turtle
None	hawksbill turtle
None	humpback whale
None	Hydrobatidae spp.
None	Indopacetus pacificus
None	Isistius brasiliensis
None	Istiompax indica
None	Istiophorus platypterus
None	Isurus oxyrinchus
None	Isurus paucus
None	Isurus spp.
None	Kajikia audax
None	Katsuwonus pelamis
None	killer whale
None	king-of-the-salmon
None	Kogia spp.

None	Lagenodelphis hosei
None	Lagenorhynchus obliquidens
None	Lagocephalus spp.
None	Lamna ditropis
None	Lampris guttatus
None	Laridae spp.
None	Larus tridactyla
None	laysan albatross
None	leatherback sea turtle
None	leatherback turtle
None	Lepidochelys olivacea
None	Lepidocybium flavobrunneum
None	Lissodelphis borealis
None	loggerhead sea turtle
None	loggerhead turtle
None	longfin escolar
None	longfin mako shark
None	Longman's beaked whale
None	longnose lancetfish
None	Lophotus spp.
None	louvar
None	lustrous pomfret
None	Luvarus imperialis
None	mackerel

None	Mackerel spp.
None	Magnuson-Stevens Fishery Conservation and Management Act
None	Makaira nigricans
None	Manta birostris
None	marine mammals
None	masked booby
None	Masturus lanceolatus
None	Megachasma pelagios
None	megamouth shark
None	Megaptera novaeangliae
None	melon-headed whale
None	Mesoplodon spp.
None	mesoplodont beaked whale
None	Mesoplodon densirostris
None	minke whale
None	mobula
None	Mobula spp.
None	Mola mola
None	Monachus schauinslandi
None	Nesiarachus nasutus
None	northern right whale
None	oarfish
None	observer
None	oceanic whitetip shark

None	Odontaspis noronhai
None	oilfish
None	olive ridley sea turtle
None	olive ridley turtle
None	omosudis lowii
None	opah
None	orca
None	Orcinus orca
None	osteichthys
None	other identified bird
None	other identified fish
None	other identified shark
None	pacific bonito
None	Pacific whitesided dolphin
None	pelagic puffer
None	pelagic stingray
None	pelagic thresher shark
None	Peponocephala electra
None	Phaethon spp.
None	Phocoenidae
None	Phoebastria albatrus
None	Phoebastria immutabilis
None	Phoebastria nigripes
None	Phoebastria spp.

None	Physeter macrocephalus
None	Pinnipedia
None	pompano dolphinfish
None	Prionace glauca
None	Procelsterna spp.
None	Promethichthys prometheus
None	protected species
None	Pseudocarcharias kamoharai
None	Pseudorca crassidens
None	Pterodroma spp.
None	Pteroplatytrygon violacea
None	Puffinus spp.
None	pygmy killer whale
None	rainbow runner
None	Rajiformes
None	Ranzania laevis
None	razorback scabbardfish
None	red-footed booby
None	Regalecus glesne
None	Remora
None	Rhincodon typus
None	risso's dolphin
None	Roudi escolar
None	rough pomfret

None	rough triggerfish
None	rough-toothed dolphin
None	Ruvettus pretiosus
None	sailfish
None	salmon shark
None	sandbar shark
None	Sarda chiliensis
None	scalloped hammerhead shark
None	scalloped ribbonfish
None	Scombrobrax heterolepis
None	sea birds
None	sea turtles
None	seabirds
None	sei whale
None	Seriola lalandi
None	shallow set
None	sharks
None	sharptail mola
None	short-finned pilot whale
None	short-tailed albatross
None	shortbill spearfish
None	shortfin mako shark
None	sickle pomfret
None	silky shark

None	skipjack tuna
None	slender mola
None	smooth hammerhead shark
None	snake mackerel
None	sperm whale
None	Sphyrna barracuda
None	Sphyrna lewini
None	Sphyrna spp.
None	Sphyrna zygaena
None	spinner dolphin
None	spotted dolphin
None	Squalidae spp.
None	Stenella attenuata
None	Stenella coeruleoalba
None	Stenella longirostris
None	Steno bredanensis
None	Stercorarius spp.
None	striped dolphin
None	striped marlin
None	Suckerfish
None	sula dactylatra
None	sula leucogaster
None	Sula spp.
None	Sula sula

None	swordfish
None	tapertail ribbonfish
None	Taractes asper
None	Taractes rubsecens
None	Teractichthys steindachneri
None	Testudines
None	Tetraodontidae spp.
None	Tetrapturus angustirostris
None	thunnus alalunga
None	thunnus albacares
None	thunnus obesus
None	thunnus orientalis
None	tiger shark
None	Trachipterus altivelis
None	Trachipterus fukuzakii
None	Trichiuridae spp.
None	tuna
None	Tursiops truncatus
None	unidentified albatross
None	unidentified beaked whale
None	unidentified billfish
None	unidentified bird
None	unidentified blackfish
None	unidentified booby

None	unidentified cetacean
None	unidentified common dolphin
None	unidentified dolphin
None	unidentified fish
None	unidentified frigatebird
None	unidentified gull
None	unidentified hammerhead shark
None	unidentified hardshell sea turtle
None	unidentified hardshell turtle
None	unidentified jaeger
None	unidentified kogia whale
None	unidentified mako shark
None	unidentified petrel
None	unidentified pinniped
None	unidentified porpoise
None	unidentified puffer
None	unidentified ray
None	unidentified scabbardfish
None	unidentified sea turtle
None	unidentified shark
None	unidentified shearwater
None	unidentified snake mackerel
None	unidentified storm petrel
None	unidentified tern

None	unidentified thresher shark
None	unidentified triggerfish
None	unidentified tropicbird
None	unidentified tuna
None	unidentified turtle
None	unidentified whale
None	unspecified jack
None	Uraspis secunda
None	Uraspis spp.
None	velvet dogfish
None	wahoo
None	whale shark
None	Xiphias gladius
None	yellowfin tuna
None	yellowtail
None	Zameus squamulosus
None	Ziphiidae spp.
None	Ziphius cavirostris
None	Zu cristatus

Temporal Keywords

Thesaurus	Keyword
UNCONTROLLED	
None	February 1994

Spatial Keywords

Thesaurus	Keyword
UNCONTROLLED	
None	Hawaii
None	North-Central Pacific Ocean

Stratum Keywords

Thesaurus	Keyword
UNCONTROLLED	
None	pelagic

Physical Location

Organization: Pacific Islands Regional Office

City: Honolulu

State/Province: HI

Country: United States of America

Support Roles

Point of Contact		CC ID: 172361
Date Effective From:	1999	
Date Effective To:		
Contact (Person):	Kelly, John D	
Address:	1845 Wasp Boulevard Honolulu, HI 96818	

USA

Email Address: john.d.kelly@noaa.gov

Phone: 808-725-5100

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Contact Instructions: Phone or email

Point of Contact

CC ID: 172363

Date Effective From: 1997-07-20

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Busscher, Kevin

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Honolulu, HI 96818
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Email Address: kevin.busscher@noaa.gov

Phone: 808-725-5102

Fax: 808-725-5217

Contact Instructions: Phone or email

Extents

Extent Group 1

Extent Group 1 / Geographic Area 1

CC ID: 172732

Description North-Central Pacific Ocean

Extent Group 1 / Time Frame 1

Time Frame Continuing

Type:

Start: 1994-02

Access Information

Security Class: Confidential

Child Items

Rubric scores updated every 15m

	Type	Title
68	Data Set	Circular Updates
65	Data Set	Data Collection Forms - Legacy
89	Data Set	Hawaii Longline Trip Log
80	Data Set	Incident Report - Legacy
80	Data Set	Injury & Safety Report - Legacy
68	Data Set	Observer Manual and Current Data Collection Forms
65	Data Set	Percent Coverage
74	Data Set	Photos and Videos
80	Data Set	Post-Cruise Questionnaire - Legacy
67	Data Set	Quarterly, Bi-annual and Annual Reports
74	Data Set	Sea Turtle Interaction Report
74	Data Set	Vessel Activity Record
74	Data Set	Vessel Arrival Info - Legacy

Related Items

Item Type	Relatio... Type	Title
Data Set (DS)	Cross Referen...	Longline Observer Data System
Catalog Details		
Catalog Item ID:	16865	
GUID:	gov.noaa.nmfs.inport:16865	
Metadata Record Created By:	Eric Forney	
Metadata Record Created:	2012-10-24 16:35+0000	
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Frequency:

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